

COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS OF HOMONYMS OF ENGLISH AND RUSSIAN LANGUAGES

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Abstract: *The homonyms of English and Russian languages are compared in this article. One of the most difficult aspects of the English language, which affects everyone, is that words with similar spelling or sounds can have very different meanings. Sentences containing such words, also known as homonyms, can cause confusion because the translation of each word independently does not allow one to comprehend the meaning of the statement as a whole. This type of word appears frequently in the language; yet, the problem of homonymy remains poorly understood within the context of the study of homonyms in the English language. The idea of homonymy is examined, as well as a comparison of the phenomena in the Russian and English languages.*

Keywords: *homonyms of the English language, interlingual interference, linguistic interpretation, speech skills, evolution of teaching methods, linguistic comprehension, psychological understanding, cultural interference, morphogenesis.*

To clarify the differences (quantitative and qualitative) that exist between the two languages in this regard, a comparative analysis of homonyms in Russian and English is required. It is obvious that the results of such a comparison are required for the creation of approaches for teaching Russophones English homonyms. We can state that comparative typology of languages as a whole has an applied meaning for linguodidactics and is in demand in situations where speech interference must be eliminated, as well as in the development of students' linguistic competence. It's worth noting that homonymy is one of the interlingual and intralingual interference variables in general. In the case of homonyms, interlanguage interference manifests itself in the sound and/or spelling of words in various languages (the so-called "false friends of the translator"). The challenge of distinguishing polysemy and homonymy is addressed by intralingual interference [3].

Domestic researchers U.K. Yusupov, M. Dzhusupov, and J. J. Jalolov made major contributions to the study of the phenomena of interference. "The reasons for interlingual interference, in our opinion, are differences between the languages in contact (between language systems and operations performed at different levels of speech generation and comprehension), the degree of strength of speech skills, or the lack of

foreign language skills," he writes. The first is linguistic in nature, while the second is psychological in nature"[6].

"It has been established that interlingual interferences manifest in speech not only in the form of a deviation from the norm of one or each of the contacting languages (in the linguistic sense) or in the form of negative transfer of speech skills (in the psychological sense), but can also manifest itself in the form of silence (in the psychological sense," says W.C. Yusupov. [6]. M. Dzhusupov conducted a thorough examination of the existing linguistic interpretations of speech phenomena.

It's also worth noting that M. Dzhusupov extends on the concept of speech interference: "Speech interference is typically considered as a one-way process, that is, as a negative influence of native language elements on the process of mastering a nonnative language." Speech interference in a non-native language is a two-way process, according to us: "Errors in speech in the target language are the consequence of the negative influence of both the native language and the target language's characteristics" [1].

Jalolov develops the idea that, in addition to language interference, culturological and methodological interference are relevant for linguodidactics in his works: "The fact is that a language, especially a non-native language, is assimilated as a reflection of a country's culture or a native speaker at the same time. As a result, over the past two decades, they have been studying the language as well as the culture, for example, teaching the English language and culture. This, in our opinion, is how the subject should be referred to. All of this shows that while learning a native speaker's culture, the so-called cultural interference is also present, and that overcoming it is crucial for linguodidactic success" [2]. Obviously, when teaching homonyms in the English language, the teacher and pupils must deal with all of the sorts of interference stated.

In this regard, the phenomena of English-Russian interlanguage homonymy, i.e. the so-called "false friends of the translator," demands special attention. This figurative word has long been used to describe lexemes that are in tune with one another but have different meanings in two separate languages. For example, the English word artist - a person who creates paintings or drawings as a profession or hobby, is consonant with the Russian word артист; book - a written or printed work consisting of pages glued or sewn together along one side and bound in covers, consonant with the Russian word - бок (type of tree); boy - a male child or youth. - cf. Russian бой; box - a container with a flat base and sides, typically square or rectangular and having a lid - English in Russian бокс (kind of sport); bread - food made of flour, water, and yeast mixed together and baked - cf. Russian бред (nonsense); capital - the city or town that functions as the seat of government and administrative centre of a country or region - cf. Russian капитал; clever - smart - cf. Russian клевер (plant); look - direct one's gaze toward someone or something or in a specified direction - cf. Russian лук (vegetable) and many others [5].

Because lexical homonymy is a language universal, the ontological qualities of lexical homonyms in English and Russian are generally comparable: their sources, types,

and stylistic functions in speech are all comparable. However, in comparison to Russian homonyms, English homonyms have several distinct characteristics. The distinctions between homographs and homophones are especially obvious.

Despite the fact that English has a substantially higher number of homonyms than Russian, their collision in the text is uncommon. This is because, as a result of shaping, homonymy, which is fixed at the language system level, gets erased during the speech implementation phase. Most English verbs that are homonymous in the infinitive form are not homonymous in other forms, for example. They are only employed in the form of an infinitive in particular situations, such as when they are in the Present Indefinite Tense or the Future Indefinite Tense, and sound and write similarly to the forms of the 1st and 2nd person singular and plural, as well as the 3rd person plural.

In general, the distinctions between Russian and English homonyms are primarily morphological and word formation-related. If English is an analytical language, Russian is a language with a synthetic structure that leans towards analyticism. This means that in the Russian language, the synthetic grammatical technique is dominant, and inflection is widely used. Inflection has lost its meaning and function in English. As a result of syntactic transposition, or the passage of words from one section of speech to another, the possibilities for the development of homonyms increased dramatically. For example, bill (the jaws of a bird together with their horny covering) - bill (to touch and rub bill to bill), bowl (a bowl-shaped structure) - bowl (to roll a ball), break (interrupt a sequence, course, or continuous state) - break (to separate into parts with suddenness or violence), brush (a device composed of bristles typically set into a handle and used especially for sweeping, smoothing, scrubbing, or painting) - brush (remove (dust or dirt) by sweeping or scrubbing). It is quite obvious that in the Russian language there are much fewer such examples - cf. homonymy of the word один (one - numerical) - один (one - adj.) - один (one - pronoun) [4]. The ratio of the parts of speech involved in the act of transposition is also different in Russian and English. For example, in Russian language, the transition of a verb into a noun or a noun into a verb, similar to the above examples, is impossible. In such cases, in Russian language, either the suffix or the nonaffix method finds its application, compare: to move (двигать) - movement (движение), to run (бегать) - run (бег). The presence of endings in the Russian language leads to the emergence of expanded inflectional paradigms, within which homoforms arise. Despite the fact that there are cases of homoforms in the English language, their number is significantly less and does not have the character of morphological opposition in view of its unsystematic nature. Some exceptions to this are homoforms of Present Continuous Tense verbs, for example, reading (n) - reading (v.), meeting (n.) - meeting (v.).

I enjoy reading (Я люблю читать);

I am reading a book (Я читаю книгу)

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